

More (enough) is Better: Towards Few-Shot Illegal Landfill Waste Segmentation.

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Abstract. Image segmentation for detecting illegal landfill waste in aerial images is essential for environmental crime monitoring. Despite advancements in segmentation models, the primary challenge in this domain is the lack of annotated data due to the unknown locations of illegal waste disposals. This work mainly focuses on evaluating segmentation models for identifying individual illegal landfill waste segments using limited annotations. This research seeks to lay the groundwork for a comprehensive model evaluation to contribute to environmental crime monitoring and sustainability efforts by proposing to harness the combination of agnostic segmentation and supervised classification approaches. We mainly explore different metrics and combinations to better understand how to measure the quality of this applied segmentation problem.

1 Introduction

Illegal dumping has a substantial environmental impact, affecting our economy and health. Different institutions across the globe have allocated extra resources to curb the spread of such unauthorized practices [13, 14, 6, 4, 3]. The primary objective of this study is to address the image segmentation task for detecting illegal landfill waste on aerial images. Image segmentation is one of the most studied tasks in computer vision [9, 17]. Even though several models for segmentation have been successfully developed in the last decade [15, 7, 10], the main challenge in the illegal landfill waste domain is the need for annotation. Since illegal waste disposals are unknown or even known, but their geospatial information is sensitive and typically unavailable, it takes work to obtain the necessary amount of annotated data to train accurate segmentation models. On the other hand, when using satellite imagery information, we need to consider the image quality or resolution that, in contrast to the study of well-known (i.e. legal) landfills, should be high enough to identify them. In this context, we face two critical drawbacks in the problem of illegal landfill waste segmentation: first, low-resolution images need better visual information referring to illegal landfill waste; they are typically significantly smaller compared with legal and traditional landfill wastes.

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This makes it challenging to identify its posterior segmentation. Second, high-resolution images are typically accessible at a significant cost depending on the platform, technology and quality.

However, as far as our scope goes, there is no abundant dataset regarding illegal landfill waste in environmental crime literature. One recent work is the *AerialWaste* project [18] that proposes a High-Resolution dataset of more than 10k RGB aerial images with annotations of the presence and the absence of waste. It is also possible to effectively build a binary classification model to discriminate between images that contain or are not illegal waste dumps. One limitation of this dataset is the absence of enough segmentation mask annotations.

This scenario motivates us to analyze the possibilities of constructing an effective segmentation model to identify individual illegal landfill wastes present in these images. Since similar datasets are not available in the literature, our focus is not on performing a benchmark between different models and datasets but rather on better understanding how the visual information utilized for classification could benefit in building models for segmentation with only a few annotations. These experiments are initial steps in performing illegal landfill waste segmentation using agnostic and supervised classification techniques.

We propose to explore two different approaches attempting to pre-

Figure 1: Pipeline of the predictive segmentation approach.

dict the most likely waste segments based only on a few annotations. Both approaches have two main modules, one for binary classification, detecting the presence or absence of waste, and another for agnostic segmentation. The first approach doesn't require any training for segmentation, it is an *agnostic segmentation driven by supervised classification*. The second approach also includes a predictive module attempting to identify which segment candidates are most likely to be waste instead of purely segment from the agnostic model. Figure 1 shows the pipeline of the predictive approach including the modules of segmentation (SEG), classification (CLS) and prediction. In Section 3 we provide a detailed explanation about each approach.

In addition, since the quality of environmental crime monitoring is difficult to reflect with the typical segmentation metrics (such as Intersection over Union or Dice coefficient), we also include different measurements for a more comprehensive evaluation. The goal is to understand the possibilities of an applied segmentation problem-oriented to sustainability by fighting against environmental crimes focused on illegal landfill waste segmentation.

The key contributions of this manuscript are:

- A novel method that combines supervised binary classification with agnostic segmentation.
- Two approaches to predict potential waste segments: one that does not require any training process for segmentation, and other that focuses in leveraging only a few annotation masks.
- An empirical study of different evaluation metrics and their combinations in order to properly assess the quality of the segmentation process in the illegal waste monitoring domain.

This paper is structured as follows: Section 2 delves into related works, introduces the segmentation problem and compares different methodologies for addressing this task. Section 3 describes our proposed methodology, exposing the two different approaches in detail. Section 4 describes the experimental setup and the different formulations of the methodologies presented in the previous section as well as the different metrics we employ for the evaluation process. Section 5 presents the results of our experiments and discuss their most important aspects. Finally, Section 6 describes our conclusions and future works.

2 Related Works

The semantic image segmentation task is to determine each pixel's most likely class label from a given finite set of possible categories. Fundamental works on image segmentation are based on analyzing the discontinuity and similarity of the image intensity values, finding abrupt intensity changes as edges and partitioning the images into regions of similar criteria [9, 17]. These approaches are typically based on analyzing the image morphology but lack semantic information crucial in our cognitive system for categorizing what we see beyond the similarity in shapes, as could be the internal structure of categories or prototypes, understanding prototypes as a reference point for categorization [16].

The concept of prototypes plays an important role when we want to incorporate semantic, as in the case of supervised learning. In recent decades, the most impressive performance in semantic image segmentation is achieved by deep learning approaches and convolutional neural networks that are trained with a set of already segmented (i.e., labelled) images to learn how to segment a new image instance, examples of these techniques are the FCN, DeepLab series, U-net, among others [12, 8, 15]. Current agnostic segmentation

models, such as the Segment Anything Model (SAM) [11], accurately create a segmented image showing all the different regions or objects present in the original input. Nevertheless, these models do not provide any semantic information about each region or object.

To summarize, two models with high performance in literature are the agnostic and semantic segmentation models, typically built under a supervised learning approach. Conceptually, the advantage of the second model is the possibility of obtaining labelled segments, meaning semantic information of each category. This is especially useful in applied problems in industry, such as object recognition, anomaly detection or land characterization in satellite imagery. To address this type of semantic segmentation, counting a substantial amount of segmented (i.e., labelled) images for training the models is crucial. This makes the problem particularly difficult in some specific cases where the information is highly sensible or difficult to obtain, as in the case of monitoring environmental crimes through aerial images.

In the literature, different datasets of aerial images exist for image segmentation. Examples of high-resolution aerial images are the ISPRS Vaihingen dataset [2] containing images with a DSM of 9 cm and six different categories (Impervious Surfaces, Buildings, Low Vegetation, Trees, and Cars) and ISPRS Potsdam of similar characteristics [1]. Another well-known dataset is the SpaceNet family [5], a set of datasets for classification and segmentation of specific categories like buildings, roads and floods. Although different datasets of aerial images can be found, more information is needed about landfill waste data. In addition, the open-access satellite imagery banks like Copernicus for Sentinel-2 are images of low resolution (10 m or 60 m), making semantic segmentation challenging for such specific domains. AerialWaste dataset [18] contains around 10k high-resolution aerial images with their respective waste labels. This is not multi-spectral data but RGB images from different sources (AGEA Orthophotos, WorldView-3 and GoogleEarth). Although it contains 169 annotated samples, a small proportion of the entire dataset is highly imbalanced, and the annotations encompass different types and sizes of waste.

In summary, it is possible to count different models for semantic segmentation with high performance on aerial image segmentation. However, sufficient annotated images with good training quality are essential to this. Conversely, performing an accurate segmentation using an agnostic model without information about the object or region concept is also possible. In this study, we leverage the possibility of combining the existing agnostic segmentation models with a few annotated segments and a significant number of binary labelled samples.

3 Methodology

Our purpose is to investigate Illegal Landfill Waste Segmentation by utilizing the AerialWaste dataset to train a binary classifier (showcasing the presence or absence of waste) to prompt an agnostic segmentation model. After this initial approach, we attempt to understand better how to add a prediction step instead of performing the segmentation in a purely agnostic fashion under the insight that adding supervision should benefit the previous approach in certain aspects of the segmentation task.

3.1 Agnostic segmentation driven by supervised classification.

This initial evaluation aims to obtain Illegal Landfill Waste Segmentation from the Segment Anything Model (SAM) but not over the

complete input image. Instead, we use the information from the Class Activation Maps (CAM) [19] after the classification process. An illustrative example of this process can be seen in Figure 2, and it could be described as follows:

- i. Input an image that should be classified as a positive sample.
- ii. After a positive classification, we compute its CAM, specifying the most likely waste region.
- iii. Compute the bounding box of the CAM mask.
- iv. The computed bounding box prompts the SAM model to obtain the segmented image.

An essential aspect of step (ii.) is that the final CAM mask could vary if we threshold a minimum score or probability for the pixel values to be considered waste. Thus, we can add a confidence level to generate the final bounding box; for the example in Figure 2, we only consider pixels above the quantile $q = 0.90$. The SAM model is able to segment the content of the specific bounding box computed after classifying the input image. Consequently, the final segmentation produced by the agnostic model will depend on the bounding box, which depends on the classification model. Therefore, it is crucial to consider different quantile values during the evaluation process.

3.2 Predictive approach.

The approach of directly using the bounding box to prompt the agnostic model has the advantage of leveraging the classification output information without any intermediate process. Nevertheless, the final segmentation is left to the image subrogated subregion and how the agnostic model interprets it, which is slightly different from the general image segmentation approach (referred to as *segment everything*, according to the official documentation [11]). Multiple segments are created by segmenting the entire image simultaneously by detecting the different objects that compose it. Figure 3 shows an example of applying the segmentation over the whole image compared to the segmentation prompted by a bounding box. Additionally, the figure shows the segment that intersects the bounding box, and it is particularly interesting since it takes into consideration all the segmented objects but is restricted to the region indicated by the CAM, i.e. the objects that are into the region classified as most likely to be waste. The insight behind this procedure is that the objects composing the image are probably a waste segment if they are in the region the classifier explains. Notice that the ground truth (3d) is composed of segments that are also part of the intersected segments (3c).

Our predictive approach attempts to take advantage of indicating the most likely region for waste detection (provided by the classification model) and the different objects detected by the default agnostic segmentation process. The key idea is to add a predictive module to the pipeline, as shown in Figure 1.

The process takes the input image that is classified with the previously trained classifier (CLS module in Figure 1). If it is a positive

Figure 2: Pipeline of segmentation driven by classification output.

sample, meaning there is waste in the image, we compute its class activation map (CAM) conditioned by a quantile q . On the other hand, we also compute the default agnostic segmentation from the input image and obtain all its segments (SEG module in Figure 1). At this point, we can discard all the generated segments except those intersecting with the CAM. This step has as output a set of segments of interest that need to be analyzed independently to decide which could be considered a segment of waste. There are two reasons for the first step; if the classification is good, the CAM gives us a good set of *segments of interest* as waste candidates. Second, we reduce the cost of analyzing all the segments in the image, which is desirable since the problem is naturally unbalanced.

The described approach includes a predictive model to decide which interest segments are predicted as waste. This implies that we must train a new model for predicting waste segments. In contrast with our first approach (cf. Section 3.1), this approach utilizes part of the annotation masks to learn how to discriminate a waste segment. To predict the final segments, we need to create prototypes of waste segments to classify those similar enough according to a distance function δ and a tolerance value ϵ .

There are substantial limitations to consider in this approach: the number of annotated masks is definitively scarce, and, most importantly, the different annotated segments are diverse in their statistics, meaning size dimension, colours, context, or any other visual patterns. This makes the task of training challenging to address. In this study, we consider primitive prototypes based on their visual statistics.

4 Experiments

Agnostic segmentation driven by supervised classification. As described in Section 3.1, our first approach is based on combining two models, one for classification and the other for segmentation. The classification model, together with its class activation map, is used to indicate the region to be segmented by the segmentation model. Thus, we do not need to perform any training process beyond the classification model. However, setting the quantile q and determining the bounding box is crucial. We used the 169 annotated samples of the Aerial Waste dataset to analyze the final results. We decided to implement the ResNet-50 as reported by the dataset authors. Moreover, we evaluate the process for different quantile values, $q \in \{0.90, 0.92, 0.94, 0.96, 0.98\}$.

Predictive approach. First, we consider all the segments of the 169 annotated samples. Once the set of waste segments is identified, we split it into a proportion of 70 % and 30 % for train and test, respectively. During testing time, we must ensure that each query image does not contain any training segments.

For prediction, we first need to compute the prototypes or features to represent the segments and determine the distance function and the ϵ value to define the predictive decision function. The quantile values are also in $\{0.90, 0.92, 0.94, 0.96, 0.98\}$. Given a segment waste s ,

Figure 3: Comparison of SAM *segmenting everything* vs. SAM segmentation driven by a bounding box and the segments resulting of intersecting everything (a) with the bounding box.

its different prototypes $\phi(s)$ are defined by visual primitives and the distances for comparing them are determined as follows:

- Average pixel value per channel:

$\phi_{avg}(s) = (\bar{s}_r, \bar{s}_g, \bar{s}_b)$, where \bar{s}_c represent the average value of the channel c . The euclidian distance defines the decision function, $\delta_{euc}(\phi_{avg}(s), \phi_{avg}(s')) = |\phi_{avg}(s) - \phi_{avg}(s')|$.

- Average density histogram:

$\phi_{hist}(s) = \frac{1}{3} \sum_{r,g,b} \text{hist}(s_c)$. For compare this features we use the kl-divergence distance, $\delta_{kl}(\phi_{hist}(s), \phi_{hist}(s')) = \sum \phi_{hist}(s) \log(\phi_{hist}(s)/\phi_{hist}(s'))$.

Formally, given a positive input image x , we denote its Class Activation Map as $cam(x)$ and $b_x = \text{bbox}(cam(x))$ its bounding box. Conversely, we describe as $G(x)$ the set of object segments computed by an agnostic segmentation model. We define the set of *segments of interest* as those segments intersecting with the image cam’s bounding box, $S_{x,b} = \{s \in G(x) | s \cap b_x \neq \emptyset\}$.

Let us define $S^{tr} = \{s_i\}_{i=1}^N$ as the training set composed of the set of waste segments provided by the few available annotated samples. Finally, the decision function for each $s \in S_{x,b}$ is given by the following equation:

$$f(s) = \bigvee_{s_i \in S^{tr}} \delta(\phi(s_i), \phi(s)) < \epsilon. \quad (1)$$

This means that for a given image x , each one of its segments of interest is predicted as waste if they are similar enough to any of the waste segments from the training set. In our experiments, we use the binary mask of the CAM instead of its bounding box to compute the intersection, aiming to provide a more precise region.

Metrics. As is common in image segmentation, we use the Intersection Over Union (IoU) metric and the Dice coefficient, defined in Eqs. 2 and 3, respectively, using the definition of True Positive (TP), False Positive (FP), and False Negative (FN). However, our interest relies on the goal of bounding regions containing waste more than generating the segments of the specific waste objects, which is a substantial limitation in land monitoring, given the scarcity of annotations. Consequently, we also consider the Intersection or *Coverage*, which is how much we cover the ground truth with the predicted segments. Also, the IoU (or Dice) could not be fair enough for our application interest; the coverage has the disadvantage of being high if the predicted segment takes a big enough region of the original image. To make a balance, we also explore the Harmonic Mean between these metrics as well as the proportion of predicted pixels that do not intersect with the ground truth concerning the image background as an attempt to capture how much “oversizing” the predictions are. It means the ratio between the False Positives and the background, or equivalently, the False Positive Rate (FPR)¹. We hypothesize that allowing more segmentation than the ground truth is better to reflect the waste monitoring but controlling not taking much of the rest. We also explore Precision, Recall and Accuracy. Finally, as an attempt to better reflect the quality we are pursuing, we decided to combine the Coverage, FPR and Dice coefficient (cf. Eq. 4), aiming to obtain a good balance by covering the waste with a possible excess bounded by the complement of the FPR as well as a good Dice. In this experiment, we decided to give similar importance to all of them but a slightly higher coverage by establishing $(\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \alpha_3) = (0.4, 0.3, 0.3)$ in Eq. 4.

¹ If P is the prediction and B the image background, $(P \cap B)/B = FP/B = FP/(FP \cup TN) = FPR$

$$\text{IoU} = TP/(TP + FP + FN) \quad (2)$$

$$\text{Dice} = 2TP/(2TP + FP + FN) \quad (3)$$

$$\text{Combined} = \alpha_1 \text{Coverage} + \alpha_2(1 - \text{FPR}) + \alpha_3 \text{Dice} \quad (4)$$

$$\text{s.t. } \sum \alpha_i = 1$$

5 Results

In previous sections, we introduced our methodology and the different metrics, parameters such as the q -quantile and the ϵ tolerance, as well as the δ functions and the different prototypes ϕ . Also, we performed experiments with the whole set of annotated images and different splits when we needed a partition for training our predictive module. A combination of these variables generates different experimental settings. In this section, we present some representative results of these settings and show different comparisons between them, which will serve as a basis for further discussion.

Table 1 reports the results of the initial approach, i.e., the results of applying the agnostic model for segmentation prompted by the bounding boxes generated through the classification model’s CAM. Since this approach does not require any predictive module, we report the different metrics over the complete annotated images. Moreover, we repeat this experiment across the same dataset splits for a fair comparison with respect to the rest of the experiments that need a train/test split. The table also comprises the average and standard deviation of the different metrics, Intersection over Union (IoU), Coverage, False Positive Rate (FPR), Dice coefficient (Dice), Harmonic Mean of Coverage and IoU (HM(Cov, IoU)), Coverage and the complement of the False Positive Rate (HM(Cov, 1-FPR)), Coverage and Dice (HM(Cov, Dice)), Precision, Recall, Accuracy, F1 Score and the Combined measurement presented in Eq. 4. Each metric is presented across the different q -quantiles.

Since the predictive approach is evaluated across different ϵ values for defining the decision function, beyond the different prototype and distance, it has more experimental settings than the first one. Table 2 shows the results of the predictive for the average channel value prototype ϕ_{avg} and the euclidean distance δ_{euc} . Table 3 presents the results for the average density histogram prototype ϕ_{hist} and the kl-divergence δ_{kl} . We show the results across different ϵ values. We report the median quantile $q = 0.94$ for a reference in both cases. A more comprehensive view of these results, including all the quantiles, could be found in Figures 4 and 5, serving for a better comparison between both approaches and their different settings.

As we can see, the first approach shows results that are more aligned with the predictive approach when using prototype ϕ_{avg} compared to ϕ_{hist} . However, differences across various metrics can be observed. There are also some expected behaviours as the increase of Precision while the quantile value also increases; the reason is that higher quantile values imply a more precise class activation map or bounding box that could also reduce the FPR (in the case of the first approach). The reduction of the FPR could be desirable at first, but when the quantile increases, the Coverage decreases. It makes sense if the final bounding box is small and the region for segmentation needs to be bigger. This observation is aligned with our initial hypothesis of the need to consider a good quality result when the segmentation output exceeds the ground truth but with a controlled

Table 1: Agnostic segmentation driven by classification map. Average (and standard deviation when testing over different splits)

$q \rightarrow$	0.90	0.92	0.94	0.96	0.98	0.90	0.92	0.94	0.96	0.98
IoU	0.108	0.123	0.139	0.143	0.132	0.117 (0.003)	0.127 (0.014)	0.156 (0.013)	0.145 (0.014)	0.134 (0.006)
Coverage	0.386	0.400	0.387	0.339	0.236	0.386 (0.058)	0.384 (0.057)	0.399 (0.021)	0.323 (0.053)	0.244 (0.036)
FPR	0.074	0.061	0.045	0.033	0.020	0.066 (0.003)	0.055 (0.003)	0.044 (0.001)	0.031 (0.003)	0.020 (0.002)
Dice	0.169	0.194	0.213	0.218	0.203	0.181 (0.006)	0.199 (0.022)	0.234 (0.019)	0.216 (0.023)	0.203 (0.013)
HM(Cov,IoU)	0.179	0.197	0.212	0.217	0.197	0.190 (0.010)	0.208 (0.011)	0.242 (0.006)	0.223 (0.024)	0.214 (0.006)
HM(Cov,1-FPR)	0.445	0.467	0.463	0.410	0.313	0.443 (0.050)	0.448 (0.050)	0.473 (0.021)	0.392 (0.053)	0.311 (0.037)
HM(Cov,Dice)	0.249	0.273	0.287	0.286	0.254	0.262 (0.016)	0.286 (0.016)	0.321 (0.013)	0.291 (0.034)	0.274 (0.010)
Precision	0.137	0.161	0.195	0.224	0.271	0.144 (0.007)	0.162 (0.008)	0.206 (0.025)	0.208 (0.017)	0.250 (0.023)
Recall	0.386	0.400	0.387	0.339	0.236	0.386 (0.058)	0.384 (0.057)	0.399 (0.021)	0.323 (0.053)	0.244 (0.036)
Accuracy	0.910	0.924	0.939	0.948	0.959	0.919 (0.005)	0.931 (0.007)	0.942 (0.004)	0.953 (0.003)	0.961 (0.002)
F1 Score	0.197	0.221	0.245	0.255	0.252	0.208 (0.009)	0.232 (0.007)	0.275 (0.004)	0.259 (0.024)	0.266 (0.004)
Combined	0.444	0.466	0.469	0.448	0.393	0.453 (0.031)	0.457 (0.047)	0.474 (0.022)	0.437 (0.028)	0.383 (0.032)

Figure 4: Comparison between first approach - gray dashed line - and predictive approach with prototype ϕ_{avg} and distance δ_{euc} for different ϵ values - solid lines -.

FPR, emphasizing that more (enough) positive prediction is better for waste segmentation.

Despite the predictive approach showing competitive results, it is more flexible and could improve some metrics when considering specific ϵ . Some of the metrics show a more stable behaviour concerning the quantile values. In some cases, the performance change is less abrupt than the first approach concerning the quantiles. Also, there is a strong correlation between the value of ϵ and Precision, which makes sense considering that smaller values of ϵ imply a more restrictive decision function, meaning that a segment will be predicted as waste if it is close to its class prototype or waste segments for

training.

One interesting observation is that the Coverage, Combined and the harmonic mean HM(Cov, 1-FPR) show a higher slope change after $q = 0.94$ in comparison with the predictive approach. This suggests that increasing the complexity of the predictive module could be less dependent on the quantile and consequently the classification process.

The different results show the need to trade off the quantile to find the best possible performance (in both approaches). Moreover, there is a need to trade off the ϵ value according to the applicability, given that different values affect the metrics differently. By compar-

Figure 5: Comparison between first approach - gray dashed line - and predictive approach with prototype ϕ_{hist} and distance δ_{kld} for different ϵ values - solid lines -.

ing the different prototypes and distance functions of the predictive approach, the ϕ_{avg} in combination with δ_{euc} shows a better performance than the use of ϕ_{hist} with δ_{kld} , one possible hypothesis is that using an average density histogram loses the channel independence information.

In summary, both approaches are competitive, but the final output may vary due to differences in methodology. The first approach is purely agnostic, while the second predicts the most likely segments of waste from a set of segments generated by the agnostic model.

By considering the previous analysis and with the aim of gaining a deeper understanding of the model’s applicability, we can examine the quality of the model output and the possibilities of querying conditioned by metric values. In Figure 6, we show the different samples of applying our approach on the same image but with different quantile values. Also, the query is restricted to a Coverage greater than 0.6, a FPR lower than 0.1 and an IoU greater than 0.2. The predicted segments are shown in yellow, and the ground truth is in red. On the other hand, Figure 7 shows two different images for comparing the different segments of each model output. This figure showcases the main difference between models; since the purely agnostic model creates a segment for a given bounding box, the predictive approach outputs the default segments predicted as waste, creating, when possible, a more accurate region with fewer false positive classifications.

6 Conclusions and Future Works

In this study, we addressed the challenge of Illegal Landfill Waste Segmentation with a limited number of segment annotations. Our approach involved leveraging binary annotations indicating the presence or absence of waste to build a binary classifier. Additionally, we aimed to integrate the information from its class activation map with the agnostic segmentation model SAM. We explored two distinct approaches: one purely agnostic, driven by the class activation maps of the binary classifier, and the other incorporating a predictive module based on learning to classify different waste prototypes.

We found that addressing the issue of Illegal Landfill Waste Segmentation with a sparse set of annotations, through the fusion of binary classification and agnostic segmentation, is viable. The outcomes from both approaches are competitive. Given that the prototype definitions rely on primitive visual statistics, we hypothesise that developing a more complex predictive model could enhance the results. Furthermore, we delved into the potential of generating queries to acquire samples with specific coverage ranges and combinations of metrics like IoU and FPR, which holds significant implications from an application perspective.

Our future directions involve expanding this evaluation by defining various prototypes. For example, we propose assessing histogram concatenation instead of averaging them to provide separate informa-

Table 2: Predictive approach with prototype ϕ_{avg} , δ_{euc} and $q = 0.94$. Average (Std. Dev.) of the different splits.

$\epsilon \rightarrow$	4	6	8	10	12
IoU	0.106 (0.009)	0.107 (0.012)	0.102 (0.002)	0.090 (0.004)	0.072 (0.010)
Coverage	0.263 (0.021)	0.373 (0.069)	0.404 (0.061)	0.423 (0.061)	0.435 (0.059)
FPR	0.060 (0.004)	0.110 (0.019)	0.136 (0.019)	0.173 (0.018)	0.220 (0.023)
Dice	0.167 (0.012)	0.167 (0.020)	0.159 (0.003)	0.141 (0.007)	0.117 (0.015)
HM(Cov,IoU)	0.158 (0.012)	0.154 (0.008)	0.151 (0.009)	0.134 (0.011)	0.113 (0.018)
HM(Cov,1-FPR)	0.319 (0.024)	0.426 (0.065)	0.457 (0.049)	0.471 (0.051)	0.469 (0.048)
HM(Cov,Dice)	0.211 (0.012)	0.213 (0.012)	0.212 (0.011)	0.191 (0.016)	0.166 (0.024)
Precision	0.215 (0.044)	0.163 (0.022)	0.145 (0.008)	0.116 (0.012)	0.090 (0.009)
Recall	0.263 (0.021)	0.373 (0.069)	0.404 (0.061)	0.423 (0.061)	0.435 (0.059)
Accuracy	0.925 (0.004)	0.876 (0.015)	0.851 (0.016)	0.815 (0.014)	0.769 (0.018)
F1 Score	0.196 (0.014)	0.181 (0.014)	0.173 (0.005)	0.151 (0.009)	0.125 (0.018)
Combined	0.395 (0.009)	0.445 (0.029)	0.448 (0.018)	0.443 (0.016)	0.427 (0.019)

Table 3: Predictive approach with prototype ϕ_{hist} , δ_{kld} and $q = 0.94$

$\epsilon \rightarrow$	0.5	1	2	4	5
IoU	0.068 (0.010)	0.060 (0.005)	0.058 (0.006)	0.058 (0.006)	0.058 (0.006)
Coverage	0.361 (0.059)	0.441 (0.050)	0.450 (0.051)	0.450 (0.051)	0.450 (0.051)
FPR	0.200 (0.008)	0.278 (0.027)	0.288 (0.024)	0.288 (0.024)	0.288 (0.024)
Dice	0.110 (0.012)	0.098 (0.005)	0.093 (0.007)	0.095 (0.007)	0.095 (0.007)
HM(Cov,IoU)	0.110 (0.024)	0.095 (0.011)	0.093 (0.012)	0.093 (0.012)	0.093 (0.012)
HM(Cov,1-FPR)	0.390 (0.054)	0.453 (0.036)	0.461 (0.037)	0.462 (0.037)	0.462 (0.037)
HM(Cov,Dice)	0.159 (0.032)	0.142 (0.015)	0.139 (0.017)	0.139 (0.016)	0.139 (0.016)
Precision	0.097 (0.010)	0.076 (0.006)	0.074 (0.006)	0.074 (0.006)	0.074 (0.006)
Recall	0.361 (0.059)	0.441 (0.050)	0.450 (0.051)	0.450 (0.051)	0.450 (0.051)
Accuracy	0.787 (0.005)	0.713 (0.023)	0.703 (0.020)	0.703 (0.020)	0.703 (0.020)
F1 Score	0.126 (0.019)	0.104 (0.009)	0.101 (0.010)	0.101 (0.010)	0.101 (0.010)
Combined	0.386 (0.023)	0.410 (0.010)	0.410 (0.011)	0.410 (0.011)	0.410 (0.011)

tion for each image channel. Additionally, we plan to explore different color spaces beyond the default RGB. Furthermore, we aim to learn the ϵ parameter from the training data and leverage these findings as a foundation for designing and evaluating a similar methodology that directly optimizes a loss function defined by our metrics of interest, as outlined in the Combined equation (cf. Eq. 4).

In summary, our study shows the feasibility of addressing Illegal Landfill Waste Segmentation with a few annotations through a combination of classification and agnostic segmentation methods. Our findings underscore the potential for further refinement of our predictive approach for a more effective waste monitoring task contributing to meaningful solutions for environmental crime challenges.

Figure 6: Agnostic approach query for three images with different quantiles: Coverage > 0.6, IoU > 0.2 and FPR < 0.1.

Figure 7: Agnostic approach vs. Predictive approach with $q = 0.98$ for two images: I1 - (a) and (b) and I2 - (c) and (d).

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